

UNDERSTANDING OF SOCIAL IDEALS AND NATIONAL IDENTITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN . (YANGI O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IJTIMOIIY G‘OYALAR VA MILLIIY O‘ZLIKNI ANGLASH)

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We are witnessing the deepening of democratic reforms in Uzbekistan, the growing development of civil society, the realization of our ideals and the power of them.

From the very first days of Uzbekistan's independence, we have set ourselves the noble goal of building a free democratic state and ensuring the spiritually rich and decent life of the people. The path of development we have chosen is aimed at the renewal and development of the state and society, taking into account the world experience, as well as centuries-old national traditions, customs and traditional way of life. The idea put forward by Sh . Mirziyoyev is to develop a new Uzbekistan, to expand all opportunities for the prosperity of our people. As the head of our state emphasized: "Every state, every nation in the world is powerful, first of all, with its intellectual competence and high spirituality.

For this reason, the issue of understanding national identity is of particular importance in the development of the social ideal . Conceptual views on the definition of national identity have been put forward in our country.

Philosophy defines the national and universal aspects of human life. In this case, the representative of each nation will have the opportunity to act freely in today's world. Compassion and mercy will be strong in the people, nation or people who understand their national identity . He does not like negative flaws such as arrogance. In this sense, Abdullah Avloni writes, "Pride is one of the worst traits that arises from ignorant arrogance, which makes a person sad and depressed everywhere."

Today, most members of the nation are gradually moving beyond the boundaries of losing their sense of freedom. In this regard, philosophy emphasizes that national values are not transient, without which life loses its meaning. Determining the life plans of each nation, or the prospects for the development of society, is not such a dry game of the mind. Highly based national goals and ideals make our lives unique and attractive. They save the life of every nation. Because the representative of each nation lives his life in accordance with these national goals and ideals. Wisdom is not in suppressing oneself or others, but in living in harmony with oneself and the world around one. Adherence to philosophy in the promotion of social ideals ensures the spiritual and cultural development of the spirit of each nation, serves to cleanse it of old beliefs and stereotypes, to begin the path of modern goals. Social ideals are distinguished by noble goals, such as the prosperity of the country and the well-being of the people. They have been living as noble ideas in the life of society since the dawn of human civilization. Such national ideals are inherited from our ancestors. Mankind has always advocated good and fought against

¹ Abdullah Avloni Selected Works. 2 years. - Tashkent: Manaviyat, 1998. - 80 p.

evil. The values of the Uzbek people, which reflect the great ideals, have risen under the influence of different epochs, especially the views of Abu Nasr Farobi, Ibn Sino, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi.

Every human being is so naturally created that he or she needs a lot of things in order to achieve a high standard of living and high standards. He does not allow such things to happen on his own. For this reason, we need to understand that we need to provide each other with the things we need to survive.

Among the great historical events that the ancient Turan experienced, Amir Temur's ideal ideas and practical work on justice are of great importance. Although he was one of the conquerors and endured countless battles, his main goal was to establish justice.² The great commander praised the fact that he ruled his country on the basis of wisdom and law.

The idea of national statehood and its positive impact on the development of nations can be seen in the example of the renewing Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's policy of international cooperation, regional peace and interethnic harmony serves as a basis for stability. One of the priorities of state policy is to bring up a comprehensively healthy, mature generation, to educate young people in the spirit of harmony of national and national values.

The ideal of the national development of Uzbekistan is to build a great state, to realize the goals of the people, to inculcate the national idea in the hearts and minds of young people. The noble goal set before us is, first of all, to completely get rid of the ideological enslavement of the old system. Second, we must not allow the ideological vacuum. Third, it was to protect against alien and alien ideas. Thanks to independence, these ideals have come true. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to introduce radically new mechanisms in the Republic of Uzbekistan" further increase the effectiveness of primary health care facilities and reforms in this area health system "November 12 this year, the effective use of advanced foreign technologies experience in the field of quality improvement, technology and digitization opportunities.

For this purpose, on the initiative of the President, based on the latest achievements of modern medicine and science, the National Children's Medical Center was established in Yashnabad district of the capital. is one of our achievements in iraising. It should be noted that the introduction of new disciplines in the education system has led to the reform of medical universities, Professor Mukhamedova Z.M. " One of the main reasons for the introduction of bioethics courses in medical universities in Uzbekistan is to counter inhumane trends in modern medicine and healthcare. Therefore, bioethics education meets the requirements of the time, combining the humanities and social sciences. " This will help us achieve the goals we have set for ourselves over the years.

Conclusion doing in particular, the ongoing reforms and changes in our country peace both security, restored development and realization of our ideals as a focused and solid foundation

²See Amir Temur. "Temur's traps". Tashkent, Ghafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1996.

serving. At any time, the development of education in the understanding of national identity determines the fate of the nation.

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